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Research Article

OSTEOPOROSIS IN PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE

SUMRA FARDOUS, ZUNAIRA RASHID

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Abstract:

Objective. To determine the frequency of osteoporosis in cases with peptic ulcer disease. **Methods;** It was a descriptive, cross sectional study that was conducted at Department of Medicine, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore and Sahiwal Medical college Sahiwal from July 2019 to December 2019. The cases presenting with history of epigastric pain with age range of 20 to 60 years of both gender were considered. These cases then underwent upper GI endoscopy and finally the 50 cases of peptic ulcer were considered. The detailed data was collected. The cases with previous history of bone trauma, metabolic disorders, end stage renal or liver disease and those with diabetes mellitus were excluded. The cases with diagnosed PUD then underwent DEXA scan and score less than 2.5 was labeled with osteoporosis. **Results;** In this study there were total 50 cases out of which 28 were males and 22 females. The mean age was 37.14 ± 4.27 years. The mean duration of PUD was 2.3 ± 0.5 years and mean T score was 1.3 ± 0.6 . Osteoporosis was seen in 5 (10%) of cases. Osteoporosis was more seen in females affecting 03 (13.64%) cases of their respective groups ($p = 0.07$). There was no significant difference in terms of duration of PUD with osteoporosis ($p = 0.78$). **Conclusion:** Osteoporosis is not uncommon in cases of peptic ulcer disease. Female gender is nearly significantly associated with this.

Key words. PUD, Osteoporosis, DEXA scan, T scorex

Corresponding author:

SUMRA FARDOUS,

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is one amongst the common presentations at the medical and gastrointestinal wards and outpatient departments. The nature has provided with a natural balance of acid production and its counter alkaline agents to keep a static and safe balance. The peptic ulcer develops whenever, there is an imbalance between these factors and the insulting agents supersede the protective mechanisms.

Peptic ulcer is defined in an area starting from the lower end of the esophagus to the first part of the duodenum. Gastro oesophageal reflux is one of the most common causes for it. There are multiple factors that can influence over this and lead to this breach in mucosa. These include life style modification, increased beverages use, chocolates, smoking, alcohol etc. Various drugs are also culprit for this and NSAIDs being the most notorious ones. H pylori is the most studied bug that is found in the stomach and lead to injury of the mucosa. There are many studies that have labeled the strong association between the PUD and the presence of H pylori.²⁻³

Osteoporosis is a disease caused by decreased bone mineralization. Different tools to assess for bone mineral density diagnose it. There are multiple factors that can causes osteoporosis in cases of PUD. Decreased absorption, co morbid conditions like smoking, DM, female gender are also common. Further more there are some other factors that need to be studied and are not well developed for their association with osteoporosis. Long-term use of omeprazole is also well studied among the recent ones.⁴⁻⁶ According to one study by Wu CH et al, the incidence of osteoporosis in cases of PUD was found to be in 9.35% of cases.⁷ While in another study from Japan in cases of peptic ulcer due to H pylori, osteoporosis was seen in 20.5% of cases.⁸

OBJECTIVE:

To determine the frequency of osteoporosis in patients with peptic ulcer disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It was a descriptive, cross sectional study that was conducted at Department of Medicine, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore and Sahiwal Medical college Sahiwal from July 2019 to December 2019. The cases presenting with history of epigastric pain with age range of 20 to 60 years of both gender were considered. These cases then underwent upper GI endoscopy and finally the 50 cases of peptic ulcer were considered in this study. The other detailed clinical history, regarding duration of symptoms was also taken. The cases with previous history of bone trauma, metabolic disorders, end stage renal or liver disease and those with diabetes

mellitus were excluded. The cases with diagnosed PUD then underwent DEXA scan and score less than 2.5 was labeled with osteoporosis. Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. The data was stratified against the confounding variables and the p value less than 0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

In this study there were total 50 cases out of which 28 were males and 22 females. The mean age was 37.14±4.27 years. The mean duration of PUD was 2.3±0.5 years and mean T score was 1.3±0.6 (table 1). There were. 32 (64%) cases with gastric and 18 (36%) with duodenal ulcer. Osteoporosis was seen in 5 (10%) of cases. Osteoporosis was more seen in females affecting 03 (13.64%) cases of their respective groups (p= 0.07). There was no significant difference in terms of duration of PUD with osteoporosis (p= 0.78) as well as for site of PUD with p= 0.89 as shown in table 2.

DISCUSSION:

Osteoporosis is debilitating condition in which there is decreased bone mineral density, which is associated with various diseases and drugs. Life style is thought to be another entity. All these factors can add to peptic ulceration and add to overall morbidity.

In this study osteoporosis was seen in 5 (10%) out of 50 cases. This was also observed by the study done by Sawicki et al that revealed that their was almost double the risk of osteoporosis in cases that had peptic ulcer disease.⁶ In their study they elaborated that this risk was even higher when they had other co morbid conditions like DM and HTN, however these cases were excluded in our study.

In the present study, the females were found more commonly affected by osteoporosis than the males. In a study done by Wu CH et al it was seen that males not only were higher in numbers but also their association was found significant.⁷ This high number of males was thought to be due to two main factors. First of all smoking habits are common in males and there is also higher prevalence of H pylori has been seen in males in a study by Figura et al.⁹⁻¹⁰ The study done by Laszlo et al pointed at another factors that testosterone has also adverse effects of gastro duodenal ulceration.¹¹ This was in contrast to the previous studies done in the past that found females as more common.¹²⁻¹³ The reason of higher number of females with this disease can be explained by the hormonal factors. Estrogen and progesterone are less in the older age groups in females which are mandatory for the bone mineralization and hence their deficiency lead to another add on risk factor along with the peptic ulcer disease.

There was no significant difference in terms of duration of PUD, however it was more seen in cases that had disease more than 2 years where it was seen in 3 (10.34%) cases. This was also proved by the studies in the past.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ However, they also did not find any significant association with this.

CONCLUSION:

Osteoporosis is not uncommon in cases of peptic ulcer disease. Female gender is nearly significantly associated with this.

Table 01: Study variables

	Mean	Range
Age	37.14±4.27	20-60 years
Duration of PUD	2.1±0.5	1-4 Years
T score	1.3±0.6	1-3

**TABLE 02: Osteoporosis with respect to different variables
n= 50**

Variables		Osteoporosis		Significance
		Yes	No	
GENDER	Male	02 (7.14%)	26 (92.86%)	p= 0.08
	Female	03 (13.64%)	19 (86.36%)	
DURATION OF PUD	< 2 years	2 (9.52%)	19 (90.48%)	p= 0.78
	> 2 years	3 (10.34%)	26 (89.66%)	
SITE OF PUD	Gastric	3 (9.37%)	29 (90.63%)	p= 0.89
	Duodenal	2 (11.11%)	16 (88.89%)	

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